

The Rhetorical Pattern In Altruistic Premises

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 24, 2021

Accepted:
December 26, 2021

Keywords :

Rhetorical Pattern,
Purposes Of
Introductions, Critical
Introduction

Abstract

The introductions prevailed in the Arab heritage, as they modeled the cultural aspirations of the era. They were based on various motives that prompted the authority at times to interfere in the production of the institution's culture, aiming to scatter, overthrow and fragment the cultural tide. Presented as a cultural mirror immortal with the immortality of the creative impact that carried the concerns of the creator and culture, and harmonized the reader and his directions, and in this context, the rhetorical pattern comes to establish the requirements of human happiness through the impartiality of selfish impulses, and the rejection of selfishness, which is introduced to altruism when it aims to develop human communication at all levels, and bears These trends are constant rhetorical data within their different formats.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5805215

Introduction

The diversity of the preamble discourse, and the dispersal of its speculations, necessitates its entry and approach so that it is possible to understand its directions and functions and to research its existential motives. Al-Bath may be extravagant in presenting it, so it goes out of its function, and the pathologist may reap fruits from his presentation, so he circulates in mentioning his writings and critical efforts, so the rhetoric performs its function in the field of persuasion on the recipient, and it cannot take its traditional forms, but the eloquence of this discourse infiltrates with colours and expressions, affecting, convincing and enjoying.

The concept of the introduction foretells what could be called a preamble or initiation, and it was marked by the sermon in the old composition, but the linguistic root taken from "qadam" is appropriate for the place, for example, Zaid "people are advancing, and the war is moving forward [1]. Next to the nose, and the backside: what follows the temples? And the front: the forelock, and it is said to the maidservant: She is the mean woman in front, and the front: What greeted you from the forehead and forehead, it is said: You hit him, so he rode his heels, meaning he fell on his face, the one in front and in front. The introduction to the book includes what we can see as the opinion of the eye in its opening in the first initiation, and this is what can be clarified by the significance of the linguistic root when it opens to the synthetic sciences and expresses a suggestion adopted by one of the parties to the discourse, so it is the book's introduction to this conception, [2].(The data provided by the author On his subject: "The introductions to the books suggest what they contain," the sermon's introduction: an introductory speech with which the preacher begins his sermon.

Some studies have indicated the separation between two heterosexual signs [3]. The concept of the introduction may be divided into two specific and general meanings, and the introduction to the book may combine and differ with common scientific concepts in the fields of knowledge, so what is the difference between it and the principles or the introduction to sciences? The introduction of the book: what is mentioned in it before proceeding to the intended purpose, because of its connection, and the introduction to the science is what the initiation depends on. The issues without a mediator, and the premise is what the issues depend on by means or without an intermediary [4], and the linguistic root is consistent with the idiomatic connotation of the word introduction, and thus the concept is clear and clear, and it suggests the abundance of the concept semantic, its multiplicity of uses and its ability to contribute to the formation of a rich discourse in criticism and knowledge.

The presentation reached its heights in the critical arena, so he went back to the content of the introductions, and he sought the methods of discourse analysis, which is an attempt to find out what the methods involve demonstrating the guiding mechanism and what it can explain in the folds of the discourse because of the presentation [6]. ((The topic is also located on another axis that extends between the sender and the addressee: it is already transmitted from the first to the second, so it is the focus of communication and communication)) [7], and this is what allows it to be defined by means of communication mechanisms in the art of introductions where ((the sender constitutes In the original preamble discourse, the main actor responsible for the actions performed in the discourse, these actions would affect the recipient, causing him to be convinced of

the action)) [8], and the sender exerts pressure on the recipient, which is dictated by his cultural authority when he seeks to encapsulate his speech to be a place for accepting ideas He seeks to summon the addressee, for ((referrals to the addressee perform a prominent function in conjuring the reader, and attracting him to what the sender says, but rather pushing him to continue reading and accepting the work)) [9]. Forming a reading horizon for the recipient who is still standing on the threshold of the text and has not entered a world. This horizon is often under the authority of the introduction to satisfy the author of the text and give an unshakable picture of the literary work. It sends messages that prepare and reassure the recipient on the one hand and the writer on the other hand. Safely inside the text)) [10], and this is what makes the procedural boundaries of the definition do not leave the horizon of the recipient in his treatment of the speech; Because it ((places in front of the recipient pillars on which he can rely in his interrogation of the text, which helps him to interpret the text, and to stand on its merits)) [11], which is not limited to a specific partial treatment; Because the introduction with this level of understanding ((is a primary key that helps the reader to know the general lines of the nature of the book and the direction of its author and the goal he aspires to)) [12].

There is a need for an area in which the transmitter and the sender share in order for the presentation process to mature and achieve its goal, and this can be found in a message adopted by the introduction in a speech ((that establishes a bridge of communication between the transmitter and the transmitter)) [13]. Perhaps the transmitter is excluded from the incident, so this discourse is ((a procedural and guiding key for evaluating the book in general, and understanding and evaluating the text by the reader in particular)), and this absence has its justifications. There is necessarily an interaction between them within the message)), and with this level of understanding, it amounts to being an artistic and critical effect describing works, creative or can be defined as ((introductory discourse on the text, describing it and preparing it for reception, and it includes, at a minimum, the elements of naturalization, formation and direction)) [14].

In terms of the creative impact, ((the introductory discourse limits what precedes the text from the introductions that were created by the author or someone else and written and the author is still alive or after his death. Its purpose is usually to introduce the effect and the circumstances in which it was written and the material it contained [15]. Those who address this art must be able to keep up with it and know its precise details and what this expressive style, its mechanisms and effects on the reader can aim at.

1. The purposes of the introductory speech

This creative path occupies a large space in the critical orbit and Arab culture in terms of its visionary role in feeding culture and all sciences. It includes phases that enrich the creative and cultural field so that it becomes a dominant feature in the fields of knowledge. It organizes the authoring process to communicate its intent and visions. It may indicate “the value of the book, the novelty of its content and ensuring a good reading of it. The introductions differ according to the authors. The investigator’s introduction, and the translator’s introduction, which is different from that of the supervisor or publisher [16].

This type of authorship may not be limited to prose and literary compositions, but may include poetry when it succeeds at the forefront of poetic groups ((in forming a reading horizon for the recipient, even if it is a stimulating and tempting horizon for reading the group)) [17], and this is what the poets’ care can explain from Where the introduction of their poems in altruistic or subjective terms represents a threshold of initiation that the creator cannot ignore; Because it indicates ((to the contemporary poet’s concern about the safety of the poetic message reaching the recipient, and the extent of his comprehension of the goals of his poem, as if the poet, through it, is stripping himself of himself as a primary reader of his poetry, and directing to subsequent readers, and the paths of reading branched in its connotations and conclusions)) [18].The creator is trying to reap Dissemination and spread, and this is what makes them develop their tools in a way that meets the perceptions of the era, for it is mediated by ((his initiation wants to explain how we can read his book)) [19], or his book or his creative achievement, and organizing this reading requires informing the reader about the steps of the achievement, and this participation enjoys The importance of criticism methods that concern the reader, and invite him to produce another reading.

2. Altruistic Introduction Patterns

The dispersal of the naturalization of the preamble discourse predicts its abundance and breadth. If the alternate premise structure depends on the path, its formats may be based on the construction of testimony for the author or the critical article, or it may be an advertising link, and the latter may be clearly defined from the beginning and maybe in the folds of the discourse, nor Altruistic premises are almost devoid of them by means of a statement or an allusion, and the introduction may become an essential lighthouse for understanding the entire book, illuminating its darkness with the light of knowledge. Perhaps books translated into Arabic have received a lot of attention in this context; Because this field is only addressed to those who have acquired the skill of translation and are involved in it, and maybe assigned to it in advance at times.

The introduction may go towards lengthening, which calls for boring, and there are those who brief ideas and pass them quickly, and some critics may hint and pass their theories and views to the reader through this channel. A workbook in this field, and awaits the reader’s response in what he wants, as in the introduction to one of the books ((And we had tested this mechanism in our book: Arabic Rhetoric, its Origins and Extensions,

relying on the distinction between projects and achievements, it seemed to us that every scientific work in this field Either an answer to a question posed by the age or an answer to a question posed by previous work. The statement and the explanation is an answer to a question put forward by political discourse and theological debate)) [20], and some of the introductions directed their attention and fascination with the foreign text without referring to the translator and publicizing it to him, as the introduction was brief and illuminated the book with hints Expressive [21], and this indicates the harmony of the times, and some of them may find in it a suitable place to present their views and what they adopt, so that the presentation is parallel to the book, and if the field of presentation is marketing for the book, the presenter always avoids criticizing the writer and directs his criticism to the Waher the criticism or the opinions and ideas contained in the book, and this critical examination makes the presentation fluctuating between the context of the text and outside it, and this hypothesis supports what some opinions have gone to that the presentation in the field of marketing the book and the book at the same time.

There are introductions that form the simple structure of this discourse. We have to enter these levels by means of procedural tools, and they are stages that we analyze their formations and types, where we start from the images of the introductions and the transient connotations they may indicate on the level of presentation, which paves the way with colours with a figurative tint, and other patterns close to criticism. Or those parallel to the text and disconnected from it to other topics, and this diversity is in harmony with the nature of the reader, as it makes him busy, ready, and motivated and filled with an overwhelming desire to read the whole book, or he may not continue reading convinced by an introduction that quenches his cognitive thirst. Since the title of the book and its temptation generate a spark in the mind of the reader, the introduction should undertake the task of transforming that spark into a light that enlightens the reader's footsteps, and then provoke, inspire, provoke and motivate him to continue reading with passion and curiosity [22]. I nominated formats for altruistic introductions that take shapes and images that may be dialogic that begins with its dialogue with the author, and it may be evaluative or critical that exercises points of view without contradicting the book. What is the fisherman's net that should not be thrown haphazardly or without prior planning (23). And this level is what compels the presenter to be careful in formulating his expressions. This contributes to the acquisition and formulation of a forward-looking vision, in which the presenter predicts the popularity of the book and its approval by readers for its features and novelty from through:

2.1 Glorification

It is commercial and publicity that seeks to guide the reader while giving him a pre-judgment on his reading. This type of introduction turns the rudder of the meaning that the recipient may interpret to the direction the author wants. It is a type often written by the publisher [24], and an example of this is what was said in (Hossam Nile), who presented his translation ((with a commendable effort, represented in translation and commentary. Understanding and then graduating to "adoption", and turned to anxiety, but perhaps the critical translator, in moments, was swept by a wave of deconstructive arrogance in which he thought that deconstruction was "the stick of Moses" that would devour all the serpents [25]. He is endowed with qualities that suggest to the reader the strength and acumen of the book, which is a result of the strength of sellers in this profession and the soundness of his views and critical visions, which is what we found in some of the introductions to university theses that print a book. Bilal with the critical heritage and his long companionship to his texts and to his great figures is one of the reasons that led him to love old criticism and to explore the artistic pleasures and scientific and methodological benefits that abound with him)) [26], he celebrates the new book project that bears fragments of his perceptions and his success is the success of the professor at the rank First. The first praise is for a student, and the second is for the text that ((I am certain that the researcher concerned with the history and development of Arabic sciences will find in this valuable text what opens up new horizons for thinking, deduction and comparison)) [27]. The reception following the process of the presentation cannot ignore the eloquence of the presenter when he ranges in his praise between the text and the presenter.

2.2 Criticism article

It is the one that employs the tools of criticism to build the presentation. Criticism may destroy and reverse what the altruistic presentation has made for it ((The presenter often avoids directing critical notes to the work presented to him because the introduction does not fit with the critical discourse. The introduction tries to form a first impression of the text and its author before reading it to the recipient)) [28], which is the impression that is positively evaluated by the reader's eyes and the experiences that can be accumulated by him during the reading, as it stems from the experience of the critic and he must direct his criticism gently and change his course from refutation to construction ((Structuralism has not ended and deconstruction has not ended, but rather integrated into philosophical knowledge And cash; they became elements residing in a body, and then this body after them is not the same body before them. Its form, language and features [29], and when you respond to reading it, you feel as if you are in the body of a critical book that raises big issues, raise them strongly, and suggests solutions within them. Foreign authors are seldom criticized: ((and some refer to the style of Yaos himself, which is characterized by sentences that are excessively long to the point of confusion. I have, as far as possible, cut them into short sequences, which I declare, and this behaviour, which does not violate the author's

intent, the surest compatibility the Arab reader to sequence his thoughts in instalments and without trouble)) [30]. Behind this criticism is the polishing of the image of the translator who finds him facing these important tasks as he produces for us an elegant and useful translated book

2.3 Parallel introduction to the text

It is the one that is disconnected from the text when it takes a gender that amounts to a parallel text to the text, and the sign of that is what the presenter gives it an independent title ((It is the discourse that has the tools that directly approach the receiver so that the introduction written by a critic they put a title for that presentation, which is what We find it in Dusaucer's book, where the title of his introduction is "Dusaucer and the exploration of the elements of the linguistic presence of man within society." [31-32]. And what we find in another book is "Close to the Introduction." And many other things are noted that are independent of the intended purpose. The book is like a booklet inside the book, and it may enter into a dialogue with the writer and aims in-depth to highlight the originality of the book (33), and uses the dialogue as a basic means to bring the separated chapters of the book and gather them into one story that depends on techniques leading to providing an understanding of the chapters of the book and the critical sciences it carries. Between the text and the writer, and watering a dialogue of various knowledge or from different sources ((However, their persuasion power is based on extraordinary talent and charisma that does not depend on the eloquence of manifestation and prominence, but on the eloquence of repetition, according to what SimoLeoni: Everything the leader did, And he said and commanded that he be offered no As an option, but as a logical result of the path of meaning that occurs directly without possible alternatives to transcendence)) [34], and these sayings contribute to building dialogue and form it in the circle of presentation, and through them, the reader acquiesces, and his share is submission based on his approval on the one hand, and his departure from the compositional pattern in the discourse Presentation on the other hand.

2.4 The rhetorical pattern in the introductions

Rhetoric contributes to understanding contemporary cultural phenomena and their aesthetics that are manifested in allegorical relationships and their secrets, or what happens within the metonymy, so the discourse of introductions with these perceptions is a form of altruistic creativity written in a language different from the author's language. The rhetorical pattern may be hidden within the text, but it is governed by the context, so it is coordinated in a way that fits with the code, and then it appears by means of persuasion to acquire and purchase the author. The manufacture of the other, so it is based on perception in his perceptions of the subject or purpose of the composition, and opinions may accumulate in it as they synergize in building a concept and visualization that quotes from the features of the text, leading to the focus of the elements of perception in the blog presented to it, and then reaching them to the basis of authorship on the one hand and other approaches that integrate With what the reader aspires to, and the pattern may go with the speed of perception, the presenter circles the reader in an intellectual process in which he bets on a conscious reader. The work that the honorable reader will be able to browse through, which is a summary of strenuous efforts, constitutes a valuable sum of knowledge about the topic: "The Symbolism of Letters in the Sufi Philosophy of Ibn al-Arabia," whose veil was only slightly torn. It is really worthy of study and attention)) [35]. The perceptual value expected from this production, we find that it requires mental juices to gain the pleasure of reading, and this falls within the cognitive rhetoric that contributes to seeing the method used by the writer to communicate the benefit of the book and its example: ((The reader will notice that some of the author's analyzes are not always easy to reach and that realizing them requires implementation Thought and reconsideration due to the originality and depth of the proposed theses. Perhaps this is what justified it to sculpt special conventions)), and sculpting may lead to the expansion of the reader's perceptions when confronted with the text. Because some of the introductions are characterized by poetic and their aesthetic values, on the other hand, there is a structure that the reader is accustomed to, and between these two concepts, what we call the perceptual pattern is generated ((The usual structure is the grammatical perceptual structure, and it is the common one that people often formulate their words on. As for the perceptual, rhetorical (or literary) structure) It is the uncommon structure that contradicts the grammatical perceptual structure, and if such a rhetorical structure occurs in the words of the writer or the writer, we need to explain it through the awareness of that writer)) [36], as well as the critical context, as the critic may borrow some phrases that require an effort to explain them to the reader Within this context, the translator tends to facilitate this language with the permissions available to him ((And what I said above is not a short summary of the text of the book, but rather a reading that tried to stand at the series of the critic's reception of the poet's speech, the purpose of which is to invite the recipient to stay at the doorsteps of the book, and discover what the reading missed). Here, comprehension mixes with reading and its multiplicity with the critic who stands at matters to reveal their cultural potentials with a piercing look by relying on the means of cognition in the text.

The format appears in another way and is based on the publicity that leaks to the reader when the book presents one of the flags to which this art belongs, and this bears the rank of martyrdom on the one hand, and on the one hand, it carries a marketing dimension for the author and the book at the same time, and examples of that are what Dr. said. Muhammad Al-Omari: ((I don't know in the market better than the book that we present here)). This represents the explicit advertisement that can be clearly indicated. [37]((After a

year, I began collecting poems that will be included in my book: Contemporary Arabic Poetry: It's Masterpieces and an Introduction to Reading It, and its fifth edition was implemented years ago)). These are examples of publicity, and it is based on the expression presented to that author by means of the ideas he wants that take advertising forms targeting the reader who is betting on presentations, so he buys the book and supplies him with his knowledge. At these levels, the rhetorical system constitutes a specific authority when it exercises equivocation to achieve persuasion.

3. Conclusion:

The study concluded the following results:

- 1- The reader may be fascinated by the book when the presenter is tempted by the style of the presenter and his long way of directing the speech in a manner consistent with the horizon of waiting.
- 2- The presentation alerts the reader to the advantages of authorship and what he can benefit from in developing his ideas through the cultural structure, which is the basic structure of each author; Because it works to develop the human being in his creative and human surroundings with special care.
- 3- Rhetoric contributes to understanding the creative process and the rhetorical means involved in the work for the purpose of understanding and understanding. The pattern and forms of culture are consistent so that it can penetrate into its fields with pioneering eyes, and this is what we can find its credibility in translation books that enrich culture and work to develop fields of knowledge due to the cross-fertilization of cultures and civilizations, to serve the human being or to respond to some of the prevailing viewpoints with other different ones that harmonize with the spirit of Arabic.
- 4- The more realistic the presentation, the more it conforms to the spirit of criticism, close to the reader, in harmony with his desires and aspirations.
- 5- The levels of reception vary according to the difference in perceptual and cultural capacity, and in this context, the presenter can direct the means of persuasion and drop them on the levels of the supposed reader, and all of this may be measured on cognitive fields, artistic forms, or monetary races, which aspire to broadcast the concept of otherness aimed at absolute happiness.
4. Introductions may recede among the pioneers of authorship, and their field remains new to authoring, and writing who want for their work internationalism, creativity and brilliance in the authoring space, so they seek the help of well-known pens to present their work, adorn it, publish it and broadcast it so that the reader will be fascinated by it.

Reference

- [1] Book Al Ain, Abu Abd al-Rahman Khalil bin Ahmed bin Amr bin Tamim Faraaheedi Basri (d. 170 AH) to achieve: Dr. Mehdi Almkzumi, Dr. Ibrahim al-Samarrai, House and Crescent Library: 5/125. (Ft)
- [2] Glossary of contemporary Arabic language: d. Ahmed Omar Mukhtar, the world of books Cairo, i 1, 2008. (3965- s d m) 5/1786
- [3] ((Spell broken signifier and open, and the introduction of all: Ole. It is the name of an actor breaking the signifier, and opened the name of the effect in the sense given by others. Both and then Alastamalen Fasih)): Glossary of true linguistic Arab intellectual guide, d. Ahmed Mukhtar Omar world of books, Cairo, i 1, 1429, 2008: 1/721 (4779)
- [4] Book Definitions of Jrjana Ali bin Mohammed bin Ali (T740-816h), Ibrahim achieve ratchet, Dar Al Rayan Heritage, Beirut, Lebanon DT 225
- [5] Summary of the general semiotics: Jean-Marie Kleinberg: translating urban beauty, the glory of the University Foundation for Studies and Publishing, Beirut, Lebanon, i 1.1436 e, 2015: 170.
- [6] Discourse analysis Almekdmata Introduction singer LabeelbnHisham al-Ansari model, d. To Alay Mohammed Babzad, Impact magazine, No. 27, December 2016 m: 234.
- [7] Kamel, A. A. K., Hussein, A. T. A., Shekban, A. H., Badr, N. R., Mezan, S. O., & Jabir, W. Q. (2021). Improvement of a New Analysis Technique of phenomenon of bullying and Cyberbullying among Students at different stages. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(4), 2729-2740.
- [8] Critical vision speech Almekdmata (cancer group scattering black Iraqi poet Ali J. model), d. Siham Hassan Jawad al-Samarrai d. Mohammed Hussein Ahmed Dhafiri, Tikrit University Journal of Human Sciences, Vol. 20 Issue (11) November 2013: 208.
- [9] Discourse analysis Almekdmata Introduction singer LabeelbnHisham Ansari model: 230.
- [10] Introductions to literary and monetary authoring until the end of the seventh century AH (the study of the structure and composition) on Mehdi Hamidi, Master Thesis, College of Education for Human Sciences, University of DhiQar 0.1438 (e) 2017: 34.
- [11] Discourse analysis Almekdmata Introduction singer LabeelbnHisham Ansari model: 234.
- [12] Thresholds, (Gerard Genet of the text to the platforms), Abdul HaqBelaabd, Arab Scientific Publishers, Beirut, Lebanon i 1, 1429, 2008.: 119.
- [13] Brief in public semiotics: 37.

- [14] Thresholds of modern poetic text in contemporary poetry and contemporary poetry: d. Judge Sadek, galleries, Najran Literary Club Cultural Foundation, Cairo, i 1, 2014: 255.
- [15] In the analysis of the speech, d. Hatem Obeid, Lord Jordan House, i 1, 2013: 59.
- [16] Critical vision speech Almekdmata (total cancer scattering black Iraqi poet Ali good model): 208.
- [17] Seduce thresholds title poem and questions criticism: d. Sami bin Abdul Aziz Al-Ajlan, Arab proliferation, Beirut, Lebanon, i 1, 2015: 581.
- [18] Thresholds, (Gerard Genet of the text to the platforms), Abdul HaqBelaabd, Arab Scientific Publishers, Beirut, Lebanon i 1, 1429, 2008. 121.
- [19] Arabic poetry reading of the book The Art of Aristotle, d. Abdul Rahim Wahhabi, provide, Mohammed Omari, the modern world of books, Irbid, Jordan, i 1.1432, 2011: 2.
- [20] Seen: Smaologih fiction characters, Philippe Hamon, happy Bkrad translation, rendering, Abdel Fattah Klilito, Dar dialogue, Lattakia, Syria i 1, 2013: 7-8.
- [21] Seen: text surrounding the thresholds in the work of God made Abraham novelist and Dad phone Tut, House Cultural Affairs, Baghdad, i 1, 2015: 87.
- [22] Phoenix Mohammed Obaid became the poet critic, d. Khalil ShukriHias, July, Damascus, i 1, 2012: 9
- [23] Identity marks and thresholds in building interpretation, Shoaib Halevy, see Dar, Cairo, Egypt, i 1, 2015 77
- [24] Entrances to disassembly: contemporary rhetoric, Jacques Derrida and others, translation, Hussam Nile, Export: Mohamed Badawi, Cairo, the Egyptian General Book Organization, 2013. 14-15.
- [25] Almenza in Badi in the naturalization of Badi methods, Sijilmassi, investigation, Allal invader, rendering, d. AmjadTrabelsi, Arif, Rabat, Morocco, i Library 1, 1401- 1980: 13.
- [26] Entrances to disassembly: Contemporary: 13.14 rhetoric.
- [27] Aesthetic reception for a new interpretation of the text of literary: Presentation and translation d. Rashid Bnhdo, publications difference, Algiers, i 1.1437 e, 2016: 18.
- [28] Ferdinand Dossosar rooting modern linguistics and science marks, Jonathan Kler, translation and Mahmoud Hamdi Abdel-Ghani, the Supreme Council for Culture, 200 m: 7.
- [29] Phoenix Mohammed Obaid became the poet critic: 9.
- [30] Identity tags in the construction and interpretation of thresholds: 77.
- [31] Smaiaat religious assets, disquisitions, eloquent and persuasive power: Massimo Leone, translation, Abdullah Buraimi, treasures of knowledge, Amman, Jordan, i 1, 2016. 0.1437 H: 18.
- [32] The status of the letters in the philosophy of Ibn al-Sufi, helped Khamisa, provide Abdel Rahman TLILI, Bahaa El Din Dar, Algeria, i 1, 1430-2009m: 7.
- [33] The status of letters in the philosophy of Ibn al-Arab al-Sufia, Khamisi, presented Abdul RahmanTali, Dar Bahaa al-Din, Algeria, I 1, 1430-2009: 7.
- (Al-Samiologically and communication: Eric Pence, translation and submission, JawadBenis, Vision for Publishing, Cairo, 2017: 13.
- [34] Cognitive studies, d. Ibrahim bin Mansour Turki, Al-Qassim Literary Club, King Fahd National Library, 1441 AH: 97.
- [35] Crafts icon and the interpretation of the woollen phrase in the hair of Adib Kamal al-Din, d. Abdul QaderVidouh, presentation: d. FadelAboud Al-Tamimi, leaflets, Beirut, Lebanon, 1437 AH, 2016: 25.
- [36] Reading of the Arabic Art Book of Arsathalis: 3.
- [37] Abdullah al-Bardouni his life and hair, d. Ahmed Abdel Hamid Ismail, presentation: d. Al-TaherMakki, Arab Civilization Center, i 1, 1998: 9.

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